

Machine Learning

Dr. S. Sridhar

Professor, Department of Information Science and Technology, College of Engineering, Anna University, Chennai, India

and

Dr M. Vijayalakshmi

Associate Professor, Department of Information Science and Technology, College of Engineering, Anna University, Chennai, India

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Machine learning is a type of artificial intelligence that allows software applications to become more accurate at predicting outcomes without being explicitly programmed to do so.

This book aims to provide a simple algorithmic approach and comes with numerical problems to explain the concepts of machine learning. It targets undergraduates and postgraduates students in computer science, information technology, business analytics, and in general, engineering students. This book is also useful for those who are studying data science, data analysis, and data mining. This book comprises chapters covering the complete concept of machine learning, a laboratory manual that consists of 25 experiments implemented in Python. The theory part includes many numerical problems, review questions, etc. This book covers Regression, Bayesian model, Probabilistic Graphical Model, Artificial Neural Networks, Support Vector Machine, Cluster Analysis, Generic Algorithm and Deep Learning. Some of the chapter highlights are given below.

In chapter 2, Understanding of Data, all the concepts related to data, types of data, big data, data collection, and preprocessing are properly explained. Linearity, correlation, linear regression, different validation model, multiple regressions, polynomial regression and logistic regressions are covered in chapter 5, Regression Analysis. Decision Tree learning model, different algorithms on the decision tree, like ID3 Tree construction, C4.5 Construction, Regression Tree, etc. properly covered under chapter 6, Decision Tree Learning. Bayesian Learning is a learning method that describes and represents knowledge in an uncertain domain and provides a way to reason about this knowledge using probability measures. It uses Bayes Theorem to infer the unknown parameters of a model. Bayesian inference is useful in many applications which involve reasoning and diagnosis such as game theory, medicine theory, etc. This concept with fundamentals, algorithms, and applications is covered under chapter 8, Bayesian Learning. In chapter 9, Probabilistic Graphical Models BBN (Bayesian Belief Network) concept, construction and inference are properly covered along with the hidden Markov model. Concepts of biological neurons, artificial neurons, perception learning theory and types of the artificial neural network along with proper examples and mathematical solutions covered in chapter 10, Artificial Neural

Network. An extension of the artificial neural network, deep learning is also covered in chapter 10.

This book covers all the major areas of machine learning with examples, but more programming on python may be added in their next edition. This will help not only the students but also the data analyst.

Reviewed by:

Prof. Anindya Saha

Assistant Professor

Army Institute of Management

Email: saha.anindya@aim.ac.in